

Rural Entrepreneurship

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Abstract

The rural population constitutes a major segment in india. The livelihood strategies of this vast segment depend primarily on agriculture and allied activities. Growth in this agriculture sector has shown a declining trend during the last one decade. This has made huge impact on the domestic production, employment, etc.. These problem can be tackled to a certain extent by developing entrepreneurship in rural India .this distinctive challenge and opportunities of developing end in rural location, and also provides the necessary suggestion that can be used in this context.

Keywords: Agriculture, Economic condition, Rural industries, Social development.

Introduction

“RURAL DEVELOPMENT IS CENTRAL TO ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF THE COUNTRY”

As women forming about half of the India’s population make a case for developing women entrepreneurship in the country, just discussed in the preceding chapter 3, so is justified developing rural entrepreneurship by about three-fourth of the India’s population living in its vast rural areas. The rural-urban dichotomy reveals wide disparities in various respects. The division of economic activities between rural and urban areas in one of them. Rural areas specialize more or less exclusively and agriculture while industries are exclusively located in urban areas. Given the weak rural-urban or agriculture-industry linkage, such as situation suffers from to serious shortcomings.

First, as agriculture by itself as a tendency to develop at a slower pace than industry, the division of economic activities leads to uneven development.

Second, since industry generally leads to higher level of output per worker than agriculture, the gap in income levels between those engaged in the two sectors tends to widen (papule 1982:1).

Meaning of Rural Entrepreneurship

Rural entrepreneurship is the creation of a new organization that introduces a new product, serves or creates a new market or utilizes a new technology in a rural area. Accordig to the **KHADI AND VILLAGE INDUSTRIES COMMISSION (KVIC)**, “village industry or rural industry means any industry located in rural area,

population of which does not exceed 10000 or such other figure which produces any goods or renders any services with or without use of power and in which the fixed capital investment per head of an artisan or a worker does not exceed a thousand rupees”.

Accordingly, any industry located in rural area, village or town with a population of 20000 and below and an investment of \$3 corers in plant and machinery is classified as a village industry. All the village industries have been grouped into seven major categories as follows:

- Mineral – based industry
- Forest – based industry
- Agro – based industry
- Polymer and chemical- based industry
- Engineering and non-conventional industry
- Textile industry (including khadi), and
- Service industry

Need for Rural Entrepreneurship

The needs for rural entrepreneurship for developing industries in the rural areas in imbued with multiplicity of justification but not confined to the following only:

- Rural industries being labour intensive have high potential in employment generation. Thus, they serve as an antidote to the widespread problems of disguised unemployment or under-employment stalking the territory.
- These industries encourage dispersal of economic activities in the rural areas and, thus promote balanced regional development in the country.
- Development of industries in the rural areas also helps build up village republics.
- Rural industries also helps protect and promote the art and creativity.
- Last but no means the least, rural industries being environment friendly lead to development without destruction.

Problems of Rural Entrepreneurship

While we have established a good case in the previous section as to why we need to have concerned effort from multiple corcers, government, NGO, industries etc....

• Overriding of existing rural ecosystem

The biggest problem that can arise because of promotion of entrepreneurship in rural areas is a tendency to catty the known technologies or knowledge and in setting up industries, which could inadvertently harm the existing rural ecosystem.

• It could urbanise the rural area too quickly

While urbanization is needed for improving infrastructure, providing education, health, hygiene, etc., it is important not to do the same in a quick and rushed manner.

• The Challenge between industrialization and agriculture

The inclination to modernize agriculture does not seem to be happening at a pace that is aggressive enough. In most cases, the challengeis primarily from the fact that is quicker to start an industry than venture into agriculture.

Challenges to Rural Entrepreneurship

There is great interest and talk in terms of rural entrepreneurship. Everyone wants to make use of the great demand/ consumption that can get generated.

At time Subhashree me time, there are a lot of challenges for an entrepreneur to ride on this need identifying opportunities, setting up an industry and making a commercial success out of it in a rural setting is riddled with setbacks and challenges.

1. Government policy

The Government and the policy makers should spend time in understanding the social and natural aspects that need to be taken care in making a plan.

2. Lack of infrastructure and basic amenities

While Government can make it enticing for entrepreneurs to set up a rural industry by giving them tax holidays, it should also be considered that after living in a modern setting.

3. Lack of ability to scale fundamental industries

Since many of the rural industries are very person dependent and have been primarily created for local market, many of the business and opportunities that are available may not be scalable beyond a certain level.

4. Lack of availability of skilled labour

This is a big challenge that a lot of industry face today.

5. Difficulties in mindset, belief and stigma:

Factors like lack of education penetration in rural areas, higher rates of school drop outs, increase in the shortage of teachers in rural schools and colleges are becoming very difficult for the country as a whole to combat.

Rural Entrepreneurship Opportunities

Some of the opportunities that are definitely picking up or becoming available includes:

• Agriculture

Agriculture has a sector needs to be looked at from an opportunity perspective, because large part of agriculture industry in India is still very conventional in farming practice.

• Non-Agri Traditional Specialities

Non-agri traditional specialities or indigenous product like food, hand made goods, etc... have a huge international market today.

• Rural Tourism

There is a growing interest today in people to tour rural sector experience agriculture & farming, living in different settings, because of the stress that they go through in their routine lives.

• Technology-Enabled Education

Technology can be used to provide service, there is a lot of opportunity in ensuring that education can be provided over technology medium.

• Renewable Energy

There is also hope for a lot of activities in area of renewable energy due to availability of large amount of land and open areas.

• Mobile Alerts

Technology has come in the concept of sending out weather alerts or climate alerts on mobile. An interesting idea has been seen good reception and in agriculture and phone of farmers. There are startups that have started providing climate and weather alerts to farmer through message on a mobile phone for nominal fee.

Benefits of Rural Entrepreneurship

- Reduction in exodus cities
- Improving chances for success in rural development initiatives
- Enhances economic condition
- Rural entrepreneurship can become positive contributors to nation's growth
- It can break down social stigma
- Enhancing domestic consumption

Conclusion

Rural entrepreneurship plays a vital role in the economics development of india. particularly n the rural economy. If helps in generating employment opportunities in the rural areas with low capital, raising the rural income of the people , contributing to the development of agriculture by reducing disguised unemployment.

References

- Papola, TS. "Rural Industrialation (Approaches and Potential)". *Himalaya Publishing House* ,New Delhi. 1982.
- Sigurdson Jon. "Rural Industries in China". Harvard University Press. Cambridge. Mass. London. 1977.
- Quoted by Soundarapandian, M. "Development of Rural Industries: Issue and Strategies". Kurukshetra , November.
- Matthai, Raul, J. "Rural Entrepreneurship: A Frame Work, In : Pareek and M. Nandkarni (Eds): Developing Entrepreneurship". Learnig Systems. New Delhi. 1978.
- Behari, Bepin. "Rural Industrialisation in India". *Vikas Publising House Pvt. Ltd.* New Delhi. 1976.